

A STUDY ON JUSTIFICATION OF TEACHERS STRESS AND BURNOUT INDIRECTLY AFFECTS STUDENTS BUSINESS INNOVATIONS AND PRODUCTIVITY IN THEIR FUTURE CAREER.

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ABSTRACT

Stress usually affects people in miscellaneous professions like : lawyers, social workers, , doctors , managers and teachers, among others. For teachers, working with students means repetitively trying to respond to their needs while instantaneously meeting the various demands of the organization. When teachers feel that there is a mismatch between all these demands and the available means they have for coping with them, stress is induced. There are six major variables that are identified to play a major role in influencing stress among teachers in Cuddalore district. These variables are Turnover Intension, Organisational Climate, and Individual Demands at Work, Teachers Effectiveness, Family Work Conflict, and Work Family Conflict. Teacher stress will result in students future business innovations and their productivity.

Keywords: Stress, teachers, Students, Business Innovations, higher education.

INTRODUCTION

In profession of teaching, where a teacher is viewed as distributors of knowledge; teachers are progressively perceived as implementers or managers of knowledge. They work in a persistent communally isolated environments surrounded by unfriendly views and sometimes threat of somatic abuse, and at the same time under a constant fear and threat of culpability for each and every action of both own self and that of the scholar. This alone can be an adequate cause for stress for an individual. But in the case of a teacher it is reproduced by other factors as well. Teaching has been acknowledged as one of the most stressful professions today. The reasons for that are quite similar to other stressful professions in the world. In a survey evaluating the stress levels of various jobs by the Health and Safety Administrative, teaching came out top.

METHODOLOGY

About 390 public and private (35 per cent males and 65 per cent females) are taken for the study. The teachers' age ranged from <25 to >45 years (49 per cent aged between 31 to 35). The majority of teachers were married and the majority of the sample had been teaching from 1 to 10 years as per the formula the estimated sample size

required is 376 the final the sample size is 390. Job Stress outcomes - Teacher Stress Inventory (Schutz& Long, 1988)

Number of Colleges Taken for the study.

Type of College	Available	Percentage in total	Required Sample size
Public	7,942	45.6 %	178
Private Aided	2,811	16.2%	63
Private Unaided	6,640	38.2%	149
Total	17,393	100%	390

The Teacher Stress Inventory (revised by Schutz& Long, 1988) identified what types of situations teachers reported as being stressful and an overall stress score. The shortened version has 36 items that are rated on a 5-point Likert scale. These items are grouped into seven categories which include: role ambiguity; role stress ; organizational management ; job satisfaction ; life satisfaction ; task stress and supervisory support .A high score indicates a higher degree of stress experienced by the participant. A high score on one scale indicates that the participant has a high amount of stress in that area. The maximum score is 180.

ANALYSIS

ANOVA

	Cluster		Error		F	Sig.
	Mean Square	df	Mean Square	Df		
Supervisory Support	75.52	2	0.18	387	417.41	0.00
Role ambiguity	143.78	2	0.13	387	1.04E3	0.00
Role Stress	74.32	2	0.21	387	353.78	0.00
Organizational management	88.84	2	0.13	387	653.63	0.00
Jobs Satisfaction	56.28	2	0.24	387	226.24	0.00
Life Satisfaction	92.45	2	0.17	387	540.45	0.00
Task Stress	92.33	2	0.21	387	423.51	0.00

The final cluster centers table shows that the three clusters differ in mean value of all the seven criteria. But the ANOVA table indicates that the difference exists among the three clusters in the mean values of seven aspects of stress level factors are significant. The significant value for all stress level factor is 0.00. This indicates that the mean values of all the seven perceptions are significantly different among three clusters. This also means that all the seven stress factors are influencing significantly in dividing people into three segments based on stress levels.

Number of Cases in each Cluster

Cluster	1	110.00	28.20%
	2	107.00	27.44%
	3	173.00	44.36%
Valid		390.00	

The Number of cases in each cluster table indicates that around 110 Teachers out of 390 Teachers are in cluster I which is the High level of stress group and 107 out of 390 Teachers are in Medium level of stress group. This means that around 28.20 percent of Teachers are in High level of stress segment and 27.44 percent of Teachers are in Medium level of stress group. In cluster three 44.36 percent of the Teachers are comes under Low level of stress group.

Analysis of variance results for Monthly Income and Teacher Stress

Job Stress Dimensions	Monthly Income/Rupees	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	F	Sig. Value
Supervisory Support	15001 - 20000	35	16.88	4.83	0.81	9.66	0.00
	20001- 25000	34	21.50	5.23	0.89		
	> 25000	321	18.71	4.28	0.23		
	Total	390	18.79	4.52	0.22		
Role Ambiguity	15001 - 20000	35	5.57	2.63	0.44	6.12	0.00
	20001- 25000	34	7.05	1.87	0.32		
	> 25000	321	6.55	1.74	0.09		
	Total	390	6.51	1.87	0.09		
Role Stress	15001 - 20000	35	15.37	4.32	0.73	14.50	0.00
	20001- 25000	34	19.97	3.19	0.54		
	> 25000	321	18.43	3.69	0.20		
	Total	390	18.29	3.84	0.19		
Organisational Management	15001 - 20000	35	15.14	5.27	0.89	11.45	0.00
	20001- 25000	34	19.29	2.40	0.41		
	> 25000	321	16.52	3.66	0.20		
	Total	390	16.64	3.84	0.19		
Job Satisfaction	15001 - 20000	35	16.85	3.82	0.64	10.06	0.00
	20001- 25000	34	20.02	0.71	0.12		

	> 25000	321	17.19	3.72	0.20		
	Total	390	17.41	3.66	0.18		
Life Satisfaction	15001 - 20000	35	15.11	4.12	0.69	8.42	0.00
	20001- 25000	34	18.52	2.27	0.38		
	> 25000	321	15.76	4.05	0.22		
	Total	390	15.94	4.01	0.20		
Task Stress	15001 - 20000	35	14.57	2.92	0.49	5.20	0.00
	20001- 25000	34	17.00	3.15	0.54		
	> 25000	321	14.62	4.30	0.24		
	Total	390	14.82	4.15	0.21		

One way ANOVA is carried out to test the influence of respondents income with the respective to job stress , the mean value denotes that the middle category that is the respondents having 20,001- 25,000 rupees salary (per month) has the high level of teachers stress in the present study for all the seven dimensions in the teachers stress variable. The F-value and ρ -value denotes that there are opinion differences with respondent's salary with the teachers stress dimensions Role Ambiguity, Role Stress, Organisational Management, Job Satisfaction, Life Satisfaction and Task Stress. In a study in Bahrain Al-Khalefa (1999) found the major causes of stress for physical education teachers to be: salaries, bonuses and allowances; work conditions; status of physical education; supervision; college facilities; workload; career development.

Multivariate analysis of variance test results for Teachers stress dimensions with type of college Vs. designation

Job Stress Dimensions	Type of college	Designation	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	F-value	Sig. Value
Supervisory Support	Public	Assistant Professor	16.81	2.56	160	Type of College 18.56	0.00
		Professor	23.33	6.20	18		
		Total	17.47	3.67	178		
	Private Aided	Assistant Professor	19.83	6.97	42		
		Professor	25.14	5.09	21		
		Total	21.60	6.84	63		

Job Stress Dimensions	Type of college	Designation	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	F-value	Sig. Value	
Role Ambiguity	Private Un-aided	Assistant Professor	18.99	3.55	113	Designation 52.16	0.00	
		Professor	19.75	3.39	36			
		Total	19.17	3.52	149			
	Total	Assistant Professor	18.00	3.96	315	Type of college Vs. designation 18.23		
		Professor	22.12	5.19	75			
		Total	18.79	4.52	390			
	Role Stress	Public	Assistant Professor	5.81	1.53	160		
			Professor	7.27	2.13	18		
			Total	5.96	1.66	178		
		Private Aided	Assistant Professor	6.50	2.83	42		
			Professor	7.71	1.61	21		
			Total	6.90	2.54	63		
Private Un-aided		Assistant Professor	7.00	1.63	113			
		Professor	7.00	1.43	36			
		Total	7.00	1.58	149			
Total		Assistant Professor	6.33	1.87	315			
		Professor	7.26	1.67	75			
		Total	6.51	1.87	390			
Role Stress	Public	Assistant Professor	17.63	4.93	160			
		Professor	19.44	2.70	18			
		Total	17.82	4.78	178			

Job Stress Dimensions	Type of college	Designation	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	F-value	Sig. Value	
	Private Aided	Assistant Professor	16.47	4.88	42			
		Professor	20.85	3.02	21			
		Total	17.93	4.80	63			
	Private Un-aided	Assistant Professor	18.93	1.04	113			
		Professor	19.25	0.84	36			
		Total	19.01	1.00	149			
	Total	Assistant Professor	17.94	4.06	315			
		Professor	19.74	2.23	75			
		Total	18.29	3.84	390			
	Organisational Management	Public	Assistant Professor	14.49	2.82			160
			Professor	19.38	2.19			18
			Total	14.98	3.13			178
Private Aided		Assistant Professor	16.47	5.46	42			
		Professor	20.00	1.73	21			
		Total	17.65	4.84	63			
Private Un-aided		Assistant Professor	17.94	3.30	113			
		Professor	19.00	3.36	36			
		Total	18.20	3.33	149			
Total		Assistant Professor	15.99	3.79	315			
		Professor	19.37	2.73	75			
		Total	16.64	3.84	390			

Job Stress Dimensions	Type of college	Designation	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	F-value	Sig. Value
Job Satisfaction	Public	Assistant Professor	14.35	2.67	160		
		Professor	19.72	0.46	18		
		Total	14.89	3.01	178		
	Private Aided	Assistant Professor	18.95	5.51	42		
		Professor	19.85	0.35	21		
		Total	19.25	4.51	63		
	Private Un-aided	Assistant Professor	19.61	1.39	113		
		Professor	19.75	1.10	36		
		Total	19.65	1.33	149		
	Total	Assistant Professor	16.85	3.85	315		
		Professor	19.77	0.81	75		
		Total	17.41	3.66	390		
Life Satisfaction	Public	Assistant Professor	13.18	2.99	160		
		Professor	19.77	3.15	18		
		Total	13.84	3.60	178		
	Private Aided	Assistant Professor	17.50	5.56	42		
		Professor	20.71	2.55	21		
		Total	18.57	4.99	63		
	Private Un-aided	Assistant Professor	17.29	2.59	113		
		Professor	17.50	2.21	36		

Job Stress Dimensions	Type of college	Designation	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	F-value	Sig. Value
Task Stress	Total	Total	17.34	2.49	149		
		Assistant Professor	15.23	3.91	315		
		Professor	18.94	2.90	75		
		Total	15.94	4.01	390		
	Public	Assistant Professor	12.07	3.69	160		
		Professor	18.00	3.30	18		
		Total	12.67	4.06	178		
	Private Aided	Assistant Professor	17.88	5.20	42		
		PROFESSOR	19.28	2.77	21		
		Total	18.34	4.56	63		
	Private Un-aided	Assistant Professor	15.95	2.29	113		
		Professor	15.750	1.94	36		
Total		15.90	2.21	149			
Total	Assistant Professor	14.24	4.19	315			
	Professor	17.28	2.96	75			
	Total	14.82	4.15	390			

To find out the relationship between type of college and designation of the respondents with the teachers stress multivariate analysis is carried out. From the mean value it is inferred that for most of the dimensions of teacher stress dimensions the highest mean value is obtained by Professor category especially from Private aided college teachers, which it denotes that the Professors who belongs to Private-aided college having more stress than Assistant Professor teachers from public and private –un aided college teachers. The F-Value for the type of college, designation and type of college Vs. Designation is found to be 18.56, 52.16 and 18.23 and its corresponding p-value 0.00, 0.00 and 0.00 it confirms the same. Hence respondents differ in their opinion regarding stress based on both type of college, designation individually and collectively. The study by Manju (2012) points out the need to establish self-regulatory model for private institutions as they have to follow

regulations, with regard to number of class rooms, teacher salaries, their qualifications, playground size, college facilities, library, laboratories, and so on. Care need to be taken that these regulations should be both for government as well as for private institution. For universalizing government and private sector need to develop in such a way that both could play a supportive role in education. Besides steps need to be taken to improve government institutions also, so that healthy and reasonable competition between government and private college could be in place to benefit all the students.

Relationship between Teachers Stress and dimensions of Organisational Climate

Organisational Climate	Supportive Behaviour	Directive Behaviour	Engaged Behaviour	Frustrated Behaviour	Intimate Behaviour
Directive Behaviour	.701*				
Engaged Behaviour	.744*	.961*			
Frustrated Behaviour	.728*	.469*	.476*		
Intimate Behaviour	.491*	.689*	.673*	.512*	
Teachers Stress	.509*	.283*	.311*	.807*	.487*

While testing about the correlations between teacher stress and organisational climate dimension teachers frustrated behaviour has the highest percentage of influence i.e. 80.7 percent over the teachers stress. And the Frustrated Behaviour has the positive and significance relationship with teacher stress. The occurrence of stress and burnout are usually high for human service professionals, including teachers. Stress describes negative feelings resulting from work that may include anger, frustration, tension and/or depression that threaten a professional's sense of well-being (Howard et al 2004). There are variations in the results; the lowest relationship with teacher stress is 0.283 Directive behaviour of principal behaviour. The next highest influence over the teacher stress to directive behaviour is engaged behaviour of teachers in the college. There are some similarities between the influence of supportive behaviour of principle and intimate behaviour of teachers in effect to teachers stress.

FINDINGS

- Private un-aided college has highest influence for the teacher stress dimensions role ambiguity, role stress, organisational management and job satisfaction, all seven teacher stress dimensions has the significance and opinions differ regarding the type of college.
- Assistant Professor have highest influence over the teacher stress dimensions than the Professor.
- For all the seven dimension of teacher stress respondents have has significant differences in their opinion based on the designation of respondents.

- Significant difference in the opinion among the respondents based on their designation with all the seven dimensions of teachers stress.
- The respondents who got 20,000 to 25,000 as salary have highest influence on job stress than any other category.
- All the seven dimensions of teachers job stress have significant difference based on the income of the respondents.
- The respondents who are having 3 to 5 teaching hours have the highest influence with the teacher stress. Except the teacher stress dimension task stress all other six dimension has the statistical significant for the teacher stress.
- Respondents differ in their opinion regarding stress based on both the type of college, designation as individually and collectively.
- For the dimension role ambiguity the public and private aided college teachers who have high monthly income have more mean value.
- The respondent's opinion differs positively and statistically significant with respect to the type of college and income individually and collectively.
- The correlations between teacher stress and organisational climate dimensions teachers frustrated behaviour has the highest percentage of influence.
- The dimensions of teacher's effectiveness interpersonal relation have high correlation with coping strategies than the dimensions teaching ability, teaching competence, personality and evaluation.
- The factors of organisational climate dimensions teacher's behaviour, frustrated behaviour and intimate behaviour are found to have positive as well as correlated with coping strategies, the teacher's behaviour dimension engaged behaviour does not significant with coping strategies practiced by respondents.

CONCLUSION

The progress of the country depends upon the quality of teachers, building, equipments, instructional material, up-to-date library, well developed curriculum etc. These all are necessary but, without qualified and highly motivated teachers, these are of no value. Teacher is considered as a core stone of successful education system. A number of external and internal factors acts upon a teacher and influences his/her behavior in implementing the education policy of nation. So there is need to identify these factors which influence the teacher. The teacher plays an important role in shaping the behavior of student especially in beginning years. A teacher who is satisfied with his job can perform his duties efficiently and effectively and has a positive attitude towards teaching, but if the teacher is in under stress then the teacher cannot work effectively and has a negative attitude towards his job.

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